

Supplementary Figure 1: Photographs of parts before (top row) and after EO sterilization (bottom row)

#08 ABS HMG47MD

#09 PBT HX325HP

#10 PBT HX312C

#11 PC/ABS HC1204HF

#12 PC/PCTG HX7509HP

#13 PC HP2REU

#14 PC HP4REU

before /
reference

after
EO

Supplementary Figure 2: Photographs of parts before (top row) and after EO sterilization (bottom row)

ATR FTIR spectra PCG863 HDPE

Supplementary Figure 3: Comparison of ATR FTIR spectra of PCG863 HDPE before and after sterilization with Ethylene Oxide

ATR FTIR spectra HMG94MD ABS

Supplementary Figure 4: Comparison of ATR FTIR spectra of HMG94MD ABS before and after sterilization with Ethylene Oxide

ATR FTIR spectra HMG47MD ABS

Supplementary Figure 5: Comparison of ATR FTIR spectra of HMG47MD ABS before and after sterilization with Ethylene Oxide